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D8.9 – GIS Based Early Warning and Digital Twin Platform deployment report

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
AI	Artificial Intelligence
APIs	Application Programming Interfaces
CAP	Common Alerting Protocol
CCLL	Coastal City Living Lab
DB	Database
DSM	Digital Surface Model
DT	Digital Twin
EBA	Ecosystem-Based Approach
EWS	Early Warning Support
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ML	Machine Learning
RCPs	Representative Concentration Pathways
REST	Representational State Transfer
RPOs	Regional Planning Organizations
SMEs	Small-Medium Enterprises
USE	User Scenario Evaluation

BACKGROUND: ABOUT THE SCORE PROJECT

SCORE is a four-year EU-funded project aiming to increase climate resilience in European coastal cities.

The intensification of extreme weather events, coastal erosion and sea-level rise are major challenges to be urgently addressed by European coastal cities. The science behind these disruptive phenomena is complex, and advancing climate resilience requires progress in data acquisition, forecasting, and understanding of the potential risks and impacts for real-scenario interventions. The Ecosystem-Based Approach (EBA) supported by smart technologies has potential to increase climate resilience of European coastal cities; however, it is not yet adequately understood and coordinated at European level.

SCORE outlines a co-creation strategy, developed via a network of 10 coastal city 'living labs' (CCLs), to rapidly, equitably and sustainably enhance coastal city climate resilience through EBAs and sophisticated digital technologies.

The 10 coastal city living labs involved in the project are: Sligo and Dublin, Ireland; Barcelona/Vilanova i la Geltrú, Benidorm and Basque Country, Spain; Oeiras, Portugal; Massa, Italy; Piran, Slovenia; Gdansk, Poland; Samsun, Turkey.

SCORE will establish an integrated coastal zone management framework for strengthening EBA and smart coastal city policies, creating European leadership in coastal city climate change adaptation in line with The Paris Agreement. It will provide innovative platforms to empower stakeholders' deployment of EBAs to increase climate resilience, business opportunities and financial sustainability of coastal cities.

The SCORE interdisciplinary team consists of 28 world-leading organisations from academia, local authorities, Regional Planning Organizations (RPOs), and small-medium enterprises (SMEs) encompassing a wide range of skills including environmental science and policy, climate modelling, citizen and social science, data management, coastal management and engineering, security and technological aspects of smart sensing research.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a deliverable of the SCORE project, funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003534.

The core of the activities carried out in the work package (WP) 8 consist in the design, development, deployment, and assessment of a digital twin-early warning support (DT-EWS) system. The process related to its implementation followed two concurrent paths that have been articulated in tasks T8.2 "Development of the Early Warning Support and Digital Twin Platform" and T8.3 "Development of tools to access and visualise SCORE data and outcomes". The outputs of the activities of these tasks are reported in the already released deliverables D8.4 [1], D8.5 [2], D8.6 [3], and D8.7 [4]. In task T8.4 "Integration and Deployment of GIS based Early Warning and Digital Twin Platform", the activities are focused on the integration of the system back-end and front-end, as detailed in D8.8 [5], and in the system deployment, i.e., the integration of the DT-EWS in the WP8 front-runner cities reality.

The aim of this document is to describe the approach adopted in Task T8.4 "Integration and Deployment of GIS based Early Warning and Digital Twin Platform" and on the related activities that have been carried out focusing on the deployment of the DT-EWS system. To achieve this, efforts were made to prepare for the ingestion of a heterogeneous dataset from the relevant CCLLs, including various types of maps and real-time data streams such as sensor observations and weather forecasts. Most important, like the design and implementation process, the deployment involved the users and the stakeholders at different stages, to ensure the DT-EWS meets the users' requirements. Beyond presentation meetings in which the system has been introduced to the users with tutorial sessions, communication with users and stakeholders has been fundamental to carry out the work, always keeping an eye on user feedback for the fine-tuning of system features.

LINKS WITH OTHER PROJECT ACTIVITIES

The activities and the related results reported in this document can be seen as a follow-up of all the previous tasks in WP8, related to the design, development, and integration of the DT-EWS system back-end and front-end. Therefore, the inputs of this deliverable directly come from the content of D8.1 [6], D8.2 [9], and D8.3 [10], which contain the system requirements and design guidelines as they have been formulated thanks to the co-design activities carried out with the CCLLs and the relevant stakeholders.

The outputs reported in this document represent the SCORE WP8 system deployment completion, and are crucial for the parallel activities of system validation and assessment, whose plan is reported in detail in D8.10 [11] (project task T8.5). These activities involve a larger number of interactions with other project WPs, in particular with WP2, since they imply a strong collaboration with CCLLs core teams and stakeholders, as well as with WP9, since the DT will represent a good opportunity for the dissemination of the SCORE project activities and results.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Coastal cities around the globe are experiencing escalating risks driven by climate change, significantly increasing their vulnerability to environmental threats. Rising sea levels, primarily caused by melting ice sheets and thermal expansion of warming oceans, have amplified coastal erosion and flooding, threatening infrastructure and settlements [12]. Increasingly intense and frequent extreme weather events, such as hurricanes, storms, and heavy rainfall, exacerbate these vulnerabilities, leading to severe economic and social impacts. Climate-driven changes in ocean temperatures further disrupt marine ecosystems and fisheries, jeopardizing local economies dependent on coastal resources. Urban populations continue to grow, compounding pressures on infrastructure and resources, thus reducing resilience to climate stressors. Saltwater intrusion into freshwater supplies due to higher tides and storm surges poses critical risks to public health and agricultural productivity. Additionally, the deterioration of natural protective barriers like coral reefs and mangroves diminishes natural resilience, leaving communities more exposed. Consequently, there is an urgent need for proactive, integrated adaptation strategies and robust planning measures to protect these densely populated areas. Without timely interventions, the long-term sustainability and livability of coastal cities will be significantly compromised.

In particular, hydraulic risks in coastal cities have notably intensified as a direct consequence of climate-driven extreme weather phenomena, demanding targeted attention within urban resilience planning. Rainfall events of increasing intensity overwhelm drainage infrastructures with greater frequency, causing widespread flooding and significant disruption to daily life and local economies. Storm surges, intensified by rising sea levels and severe storms, exacerbate flood events by pushing seawater inland, dramatically increasing inundation areas. Additionally, climate-driven changes in precipitation patterns lead to unpredictably fluctuating river discharge rates, further complicating flood risk management and water resource planning. Existing flood-control structures, such as levees, dikes, and pumping stations, frequently prove insufficient to withstand these heightened hydraulic pressures, revealing critical vulnerabilities in urban infrastructure. These hydraulic stresses also accelerate erosion of protective coastal barriers and destabilize shorelines, heightening the exposure of built environments. Addressing these evolving hydraulic challenges necessitates innovative, integrated approaches combining advanced hydraulic modeling, infrastructure upgrades, and EBAs, aimed at safeguarding urban communities from escalating flood risks.

EBAs play a crucial role in mitigating hydraulic risks in coastal cities by harnessing and enhancing the inherent protective capacity of natural ecosystems. Techniques such as restoring mangroves, wetlands, and coastal dunes act as natural barriers that absorb wave energy, reduce storm surge impact, and minimize flooding. Green infrastructure approaches, including urban rain gardens, permeable pavements, and bioswales, effectively manage excess stormwater, promoting infiltration and reducing surface runoff. Additionally, these solutions contribute to biodiversity conservation, habitat restoration, and improved water quality, generating significant ecological co-benefits. By integrating EBAs into urban planning, cities can enhance resilience to climate extremes while also providing community amenities, recreational spaces, and overall improvements in urban aesthetics and quality of life. Furthermore, EBAs tend to be cost-effective compared to traditional engineered infrastructures, often requiring less maintenance and providing sustainable long-term protection. To maximize their effectiveness, it is essential to strategically combine EBAs with existing hydraulic structures, thus creating comprehensive, multi-layered approaches to climate adaptation in coastal areas.

The effective management and mitigation of risks in coastal cities increasingly rely on advanced technological solutions capable of integrating diverse data streams and providing timely alerts and visualizations. Within this context, the WP8 of the SCORE project has focused extensively on the design, development, deployment, and assessment of a sophisticated Digital Twin—Early Warning Support system. This innovative system aims to enhance

the resilience and preparedness of coastal communities through the seamless integration of digital twin (DT) technologies with real-time early warning support (EWS) capabilities.

The approach towards deploying such systems typically involves several coordinated stages that carefully balance technological integration with practical usability. This involves creating robust platforms capable of aggregating and interpreting various data types, including geographic information, sensor outputs, and dynamic meteorological conditions. Within the SCORE project, the DT-EWS system is the platform with these capabilities [1], [3]. A fundamental aspect that is preparatory to this deployment approach is ensuring compatibility and interoperability across system components, allowing smooth interaction between the data management back-end and the visualization front-end [5].

To further enhance deployment effectiveness, particular emphasis is often placed on user engagement and stakeholder collaboration. Such involvement is not limited to the later stages but begins early, with continuous consultation, practical training, and iterative adjustments based on user feedback. This approach ensures the system remains relevant, user-centric, and capable of addressing the specific and evolving needs of its intended users.

1.1. Scope of the document

This document outlines the typical deployment methodologies and strategic considerations necessary for successfully implementing such a comprehensive early warning and data integration system, emphasizing the importance of iterative feedback and collaborative interactions with end-users to optimize system performance and relevance in addressing the complex requirements of coastal stakeholders.

Although the detailed description of the system is reported in [1] – [4], the system architecture is briefly outlined in the first sections of the document to facilitate its understanding. However, the interested reader can find in these deliverables not only the system description in detail, but also the due references to the relevant literature. Then, the methodologies and strategic approaches undertaken during Task T8.4 are specifically outlined, emphasizing the deployment phase of the DT-EWS. The key to the successful deployment was the comprehensive preparation for ingesting diverse datasets sourced from coastal cities. These included various geographic and thematic maps, sensor-based observations, and continuous real-time streams of meteorological data. Moreover, the critical importance of stakeholder involvement and feedback is recognized. Emphasizing the importance of iterative feedback and collaborative interactions with end-users is vital to optimizing system performance and giving relevance in addressing the complex requirements of coastal stakeholders. To achieve this, the deployment process actively engaged end-users at multiple stages—from preliminary training and system familiarization sessions to ongoing dialogues designed to refine system functionalities in response to user insights and needs.

Ultimately, the approach described herein followed for the integration and deployment process of the SCORE DT-EWS, highlights the significance of user participation and collaborative efforts in ensuring that the final deployed system robustly meets the evolving requirements of the SCORE CCLs stakeholders.

2. A BRIEF SYSTEM OVERVIEW

2.1. System architecture

The high-level system architecture is depicted in Figure 1, where the main functional building blocks are reported. The detailed description of the system is reported in [1] – [4]. Here, we report a summary of the system structure and functionalities which are strictly necessary for a complete understanding of the contents of the present document.

As depicted in Figure 1, users interact with the DT-EWS through a front-end Graphical User Interface (GUI), which enables them to visualize baseline city data presented as various informative layers, including the city's Digital Surface Model (DSM), sensor location maps within the urban area, and other maps or layers uploaded by users. The back-end portion of the system includes a database (DB) that stores baseline information specific to the user's coastal city, as well as data associated with user-generated scenarios, such as weather events, sea state conditions, river discharge incidents, and EBAs. Additionally, the database stores outputs generated by the system, allowing users to either view these outputs directly within the GUI or download them to a local repository.

To ensure seamless integration between the front-end and back-end components, as well as effective internal communication, the system utilizes Representational State Transfer (REST) Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). These APIs play a critical role within the system by enabling GUI-triggered function calls and facilitating data exchange among various system components. Furthermore, they support the retrieval of information from weather forecast services, establish connectivity with the sensor network deployed in the urban area to access real-time data streams, and enable data exchanges with external data repositories.

Figure 1. Overview of the DT-EWS system architecture. GUI: Graphical user interface; DB: Database; USE: User scenario evaluation; API: Application programming interface; EWS: Early warning support.

The system back-end consists of two primary components: the User Scenario Evaluation (USE) subsystem and the Early-Warning Support subsystem. The USE subsystem enables users to perform simulations for conducting what-if and long-term analyses. These simulations blend actual, ground-truth data from coastal urban areas with

hypothetical inputs, such as potential weather conditions, sea states, and hypothetical EBAs planned within the study area.

Conversely, the EWS subsystem operates continuously and independently, without requiring user input, to monitor real-time weather conditions. Utilizing real-time sensor data collected throughout the study area and weather forecasts, this subsystem predicts the city's flood risk. When flooding is anticipated at levels threatening residents' safety or risking significant economic loss, the EWS subsystem generates alerts. This capability is achieved through artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) algorithms that process live sensor inputs and weather prediction data. In this subsystem, user interaction is limited to reviewing simulation statuses, examining output data, and performing minor additional tasks.

3. SYSTEM INPUT DATA

The SCORE DT-EWS can handle numerous diverse inputs originating from various data sources. Some of these inputs are static, others are supplied by users when creating simulation scenarios, and additional data is derived from sensors. User-provided data can include actual maps as well as hypothetical scenarios, enabling users to evaluate how these scenarios might influence the hydraulic conditions in their coastal cities.

3.1. City baseline data

The city baseline data comprise static datasets that can be directly integrated into the system, as they are expected to remain largely unchanged over extended periods. These datasets constitute the essential information required by the DT-EWS system to conduct accurate and comprehensive simulations, ensuring that all fundamental functionalities are met. They are represented through accurate maps tailored specifically for each coastal city's study area. Specifically, the system requires:

1. A DSM of the city, including nearshore bathymetry. High spatial resolution DSM data are preferred, ideally provided in .shp file format or similar, like GeoTIFF. Maps with grid resolutions of 2m × 2m are optimal for detailed flood modeling but result in increased computational demands. To balance detail with processing efficiency, the implemented system currently uses maps with a 4m × 4m resolution.
2. A land use and land cover map for the study area, containing essential information on the Manning roughness coefficient and terrain porosity.
3. Detailed river geometries within the city area, including coordinates of the river centerlines, bed widths, Manning roughness coefficients, and bed elevations.
4. Exposure and vulnerability maps were developed within the SCORE project, covering the coastal cities under study. These maps identify critical elements at risk during catastrophic events, such as population, buildings, and transportation infrastructures (roads and railway networks). The exposure models differentiate between building characteristics and usage and account for potential financial losses resulting from extreme events.

3.2. Climate and Weather Data

In addition to city map layer data, it is crucial to incorporate data reflecting short-term weather changes and long-term climate evolutions. Long-term climate datasets originate from climate models focused on sea storm surges and river discharges. These datasets include historical records from 1956 to 2005 or projections based on Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) defined by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). Currently, the DT-EWS system utilizes data from RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios [6], which correspond to medium and high-risk levels, respectively, across two distinct 50-year periods: 2015-2065 and 2045-2095. Users can choose among various future scenarios characterized by different risk levels and time spans, selecting events with return periods of 5, 25, 50, 100, 200, or 500 years. These projections are an output of WP3, that elaborated them on purpose for the WP8 frontrunners CCLS, to be integrated in the DT-EWS.

Short-term weather forecasts represent an additional essential source of data. For accurate monitoring of a city's current hydraulic situation, the system requires up-to-date forecasts detailing precipitation intensity, duration, and distribution, river discharge, sea conditions, and storm surge risks. Local meteorological services provide these data at regular intervals, typically every few hours, specific to each coastal city.

3.3. Data from sensors

To effectively implement a system capable of monitoring the current conditions of a coastal city, it is essential to utilize reliable data collected from various sensors distributed throughout the area. Both historical and real-time datasets play significant roles in designing and operating the system. The critical parameters that the system should monitor include:

1. Precipitation intensity, particularly rainfall rate (mm/h), gathered using rain gauges.
2. River flow rates (m³/s) or water levels (m).
3. Sea condition parameters, specifically:
 - Tide levels (m) recorded by tide gauges.
 - Wave height (m) and period (s) from wave gauges.
4. Conditions of the sewage network for stormwater drainage monitored through dedicated sensors measuring levels or other relevant parameters, where available.

Additional weather-related data, such as humidity, temperature, wind speed, and direction, as well as data from other sensors like phreatimeters, can also be valuable, particularly for user visualization purposes. Furthermore, historical sensor data related to past extreme weather events can significantly contribute to system training and validation.

Figure 2. Example of user actions on the GUI for the implementation of EBAs.

3.4. User inputs

System users can provide additional inputs beyond those previously mentioned. It is important to notice that only authorised users can access the system with their own personal credentials. Specifically, when setting up scenarios

for what-if simulations, users can introduce data series for weather and hydrological events, either based on user-defined parameters or derived from actual climate and sea-state model projections [6]. Users can define simulation durations and input specific data such as rainfall rates (mm/h), average sea-state levels (m), and river discharges (m^3/s). For example, Figure 2 (a) illustrates user-entered data for simulating a rainfall event, with rain rates provided in mm/s. In this instance, the parameters are updated every 15 minutes, although users can freely select different time intervals. Inputs regarding sea tide levels, storm surges, and river discharges follow a similar approach.

Additionally, users can specify potential solutions based on environment-based approaches or EBAs [7]. EBAs can be selected from predefined lists tailored to each coastal city, allowing users to test these solutions through simulations. Users can specify EBA locations directly on the study area map by creating polygons, as shown in Figure 2 (b), where two areas—one on each side of the river—are highlighted. By applying EBAs, users effectively alter land use within these polygons, associating each EBA with distinct Manning coefficients, terrain porosity, and curve numbers. Furthermore, users have the option to adjust terrain elevations before finalizing each polygon, enabling localized modifications to the DSM.

4. INVOLVED COASTAL CITIES AND THEIR FEATURES

The SCORE project involves a total of 10 CCLs, three of which are the frontrunners of WP8 involved in the co-design and co-creation of the DT-EWS system. In the following, their main features as coastal cities are described.

4.1. The WP8 frontrunners CCLs

The DT-EWS system has been designed focusing on the needs of coastal cities, following participatory approaches for its co-design and co-development. The DT-EWS system has been deployed in three European coastal areas, namely Massa (Italy), Vilanova i la Geltrú (Spain), in the Mediterranean Sea, and Oarsoaldea (Spain), in the Atlantic coast. Throughout this process, the system developers came into contact with the reality of those cities, through the interactions with the stakeholders, and also social and economic factors came directly or indirectly into play in the system requirements definition.

The geographical position and satellite images of these cities are shown in Figure 3. Continuous interaction between system developers, target users and stakeholders ensured proper mapping of user needs into system requirements, while continuous collection of feedback has supported the DT-EWS updates, bug fixing, and fine tuning of the system design. The system co-design activities have been crucial to accurately catch the users' needs and to properly tailor the system functionalities.

Figure 3. WP8 front-runner CCLs. Geographical position of the CCLs (a). Aerial views of: Massa, Italy (b); Vilanova i la Geltrú, Spain (c); Oarsoaldea, Spain (d).

4.1.1. Massa (Italy)

Massa, whose satellite view is depicted in Figure 3 (b), is a city in the Tuscany region of Italy, and it is situated between the Apuan Alps and the Ligurian Sea, forming part of the Massa-Carrara province. With a rich historical background and a strategic coastal position, Massa embodies a unique blend of traditional industries, scenic beauty, and evolving societal dynamics. Its location near the Tyrrhenian coast has significantly shaped its economic and social structure, making it an important node in the northwestern part of Tuscany. The city is crossed by the Frigido, a small river originating from the nearby mountains and flowing into the Ligurian Sea. Together with other smaller canals, this river can cause riverine floods in case of extreme events.

Economically, Massa's identity has long been tied to the marble industry, shared with its sister city, Carrara. The Apuan Alps are globally renowned for their high-quality white marble, which has been quarried since Roman times. This natural resource has been a major economic driver for centuries. Though modern quarrying has become more mechanized and environmentally regulated, the marble industry remains a central pillar of the local economy, employing many people also in related sectors. In addition to marble, Massa's coastal location has encouraged the development of other activities, particularly tourism and light industry. The city's proximity to the sea has made it a seasonal destination for Italian and European tourists seeking less crowded alternatives to more commercial Tuscan resorts. The Marina di Massa area, with its beaches and seaside promenades, is particularly popular in the summer months. This seasonal influx of visitors supports the hospitality, retail, and food service sectors, providing a significant boost to the local economy. The industrial base of Massa has also diversified over the years, with small and medium-sized enterprises active in manufacturing, metalwork, and chemical processing. The presence of nearby ports, including those in Carrara and La Spezia, supports commercial trade and logistics, while regional transport links connect Massa efficiently to Pisa, Florence, and Genoa.

Societally, Massa is characterized by a strong sense of local identity, rooted in Tuscan traditions, dialects, and communal life. Public spaces, such as piazzas and cafes, function as vital meeting points for residents, reinforcing a culture of community and daily social exchange. Culturally, the city hosts several festivals and events, which are important in maintaining a sense of continuity and belonging, while also offering opportunities for cultural tourism.

Massa's coastal environment also plays a key role in shaping the local lifestyle. The sea is not only a backdrop for leisure but also a part of the local identity. Residents enjoy beach activities, seafood cuisine, and a Mediterranean climate that fosters outdoor living and well-being. The balance between the sea and the mountains gives Massa a unique environmental character that influences everything from dietary habits to recreational preferences.

4.1.2. Vilanova i la Geltrú (Spain)

Vilanova i la Geltrú, whose satellite view is depicted in Figure 3 (c), is located on the Mediterranean coast of Catalonia, just 45 km southwest of Barcelona, and it is a vibrant and historically rich town that plays a significant role in the regional economy and society. As the capital of the comarca of Garraf, Vilanova has evolved from a traditional fishing village into a dynamic urban center that balances its historical roots with modern economic activities. Its coastal location profoundly influences both its economic structure and societal identity. The city is crossed by an intermittent river, the Torrent de la Piera, that flows into the Balearic Sea, and that can cause damages in case of extreme rains.

Economically, Vilanova i la Geltrú benefits greatly from its strategic coastal position. Historically, the sea provided the basis for the town's development through fishing and maritime trade. Although the fishing industry has diminished in scale over time, the town still maintains an active fishing port and daily fish market, preserving its maritime heritage. Today, tourism, commerce, and technology have largely taken the lead in driving local economic

growth. Tourism in Vilanova is fueled by its attractive beaches, historical center, and cultural events, particularly during the summer months. Its well-maintained beaches, waterfront promenade, and marina attract both domestic and international tourists, thereby boosting the hospitality and retail sectors.

In recent decades, the town has also positioned itself as a hub for education and innovation. The presence of the Polytechnic School of Engineering (a branch of the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya) contributes to a growing local tech and research scene. This development has spurred the growth of knowledge-based industries and fostered a younger, more international demographic.

Societally, Vilanova i la Geltrú is marked by a strong sense of community and a distinct Catalan identity. The town is known for its cultural vitality, with numerous festivals, such as the Festa Major and the Carnival celebrations.

The coastal nature of the town also influences its lifestyle and social dynamics. There is a strong connection to the sea in everyday life, from cuisine to recreational activities. Nautical sports such as sailing, paddleboarding, and beach volleyball are popular and contribute to a healthy, outdoor-oriented lifestyle. The harbor and seafront area are social hubs, where residents gather in cafés and restaurants, blending economic activity with social interaction. Moreover, the quality of life in Vilanova is considered high, due to a combination of natural beauty, cultural richness, and solid infrastructure.

4.1.3. Oarsoaldea (Spain)

Oarsoaldea, whose satellite view is depicted in Figure 3 (d), is not a single city, but rather a comarca (county or district) located in the province of Gipuzkoa in the Basque Country, Northern Spain. It comprises several municipalities, the most prominent being Errenteria, Pasaia, Lezo, and Oiartzun. Situated along the Bay of Biscay and near the French border, Oarsoaldea's coastal and mountainous geography has played a vital role in shaping its economic and societal identity. Historically industrial, yet culturally rich and increasingly diversified, Oarsoaldea reflects the resilience and innovation characteristic of the broader Basque region. The small river Oiartzun crosses the comarca and, before becoming larger flowing into the Ria de Pasaia, forming the natural harbor, it reaches the Atlantic Ocean.

Economically, Oarsoaldea has long been a center of maritime and industrial activity. Its strategic location on the Cantabrian coast, with the important port of Pasaia at its core, has anchored the local economy for centuries. The port, protected by a narrow natural inlet, is one of the key commercial harbors in northern Spain. It handles freight, fishing, and shipbuilding operations, and continues to support a range of maritime industries. Shipbuilding, in particular, has been central to the area's identity since at least the early modern period. Though heavy industry has declined in recent decades, Oarsoaldea has adapted by fostering logistics, advanced manufacturing, and services. Economic redevelopment programs have aimed at modernizing infrastructure and attracting investment, while supporting small and medium-sized enterprises. In recent years, there has been a notable effort to shift towards sustainable and technology-driven economic models, including renewable energy and digital innovation.

Tourism, though not as dominant as in other coastal areas of the Basque Country like San Sebastián, is a growing sector. Visitors are drawn to the region for its dramatic coastal landscapes, such as the cliffs of Jaizkibel, the historical charm of fishing villages like Pasaia, and the cultural offerings of towns like Errenteria, but at the same time the region's maritime heritage is preserved and promoted through different initiatives.

The proximity to the sea shapes daily life and community interaction and fishing still holds symbolic importance. The sea provides a source of recreation, with activities like rowing, sailing, and coastal hiking deeply embedded in the local lifestyle.

Socially, the area also benefits from a strong cooperative and solidarity-based ethos, a hallmark of the Basque economy. This is visible in community projects, local governance, and educational initiatives, which emphasize inclusion, sustainability, and resilience.

4.2. EWS: integration with sensors, weather forecasts

The deployment setup of the EWS application uses Docker Compose [13] to separate it into several interconnected services. There is a PostgreSQL database for data storage and RabbitMQ for message queuing. The main application (app) handles web requests via Gunicorn+Django [14], [15], while dedicated Celery workers process background tasks, with one specifically for simulations. Specifically, the EWS task is launched periodically (every 15 minutes) using Celery's scheduler manager. All application-related services share the same build and mount configuration files, work directories, and data volumes.

The SensorThings API, developed by the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) 11[15][16], defines an open, consistent framework for linking IoT sensors, data streams, and applications via the Web. As an open standard, it ensures both syntactic and semantic interoperability across the Internet of Things. While protocols like CoAP, MQTT, HTTP, and 6LoWPAN enable data exchange between IoT systems, the SensorThings API focuses on making that exchanged data both usable and understandable. Additionally, because it's an OGC specification, it can be seamlessly integrated into existing Geographic Information Systems or Spatial Data Infrastructures. As regards the sensor data retrieval via the TERO SensorThings API, the EWS retrieves and processes sensor observations from the SensorThings API at the following link:

<https://score.sta.tero.gr/v1.1>

It constructs API requests by converting timestamps to UTC ISO 8601, filtering Observations for a specific Datastream ID within a given time range and selecting only resultTime and result fields, while adhering to a server limit of 1000 observations per request. To overcome this limit, the function employs a pagination while loop, repeatedly sending GET requests and appending results from the "value" array until no @iot.nextLink is provided. Finally, it performs post-retrieval processing, transforming data coming from sensors, e.g., applying a rating curve [17] to rivers whose sensors are sited far from the border of the urban study area, or converting accumulated rainfall (mm) to mm/h.

A set of dedicated APIs is employed also to collect the data from the local weather services, in particular from:

- o Consorzio LaMMA, for the city of Massa
- o Meteocat, for the city of Vilanova i la Geltrú
- o Euskalmet, for the city of Oarsoaldea.

Updated weather data are taken from these services and employed by the EWS for the flood hazard predictions.

5. METHODOLOGY IN THE DT-EWS DEPLOYMENT

Figure 4. Flow diagram of the overall deployment methodology.

5.1. System deployment process

The diagram in Figure 4 outlines the detailed deployment process of the SCORE DT-EWS system, designed to support urban planning in the WP8 front runners CCLLs. The deployment workflow is systematically divided into three key phases: Co-design, Co-creation, and Co-validation, each involving distinct activities and decision-making processes.

The first phase, related to Co-design, has been the main focus of the first part of the project, in particular for tasks T8.1, but also for T8.2, and T8.3. It emphasized collaboration between system developers and users to ensure that the system meets specific user requirements effectively. This phase initiated with the collection of user needs, where stakeholders and end-users actively participate in identifying their requirements and expectations from the digital twin system. This collaborative identification was followed by a comprehensive definition of system requirements [8]-[10], clarifying functional and non-functional criteria necessary for the effective operation of the DT-EWS. The output of these two initial steps fed directly into the system design, which synthesized the user inputs into technical specifications and architectural planning. During this critical step, regular checks and iterative validations with users were integral, ensuring that the designed system accurately reflects users' expectations and accommodates necessary adjustments before progressing further.

Following the successful completion of the co-design phase, the process entered the Co-creation phase. This phase commenced with systematic bench testing of the DT-EWS system to verify if all functionalities align with the predefined requirements. When everything ran correctly, the system was put in a test environment, where developers and other technical partners of WP8 could test the whole system back-end and front-end, by simulating a large number of scenarios. If tests revealed deficiencies or issues, the system returned to the testing stage for correction and reevaluation, with some variation to the system design, if needed, iterating as necessary until it met all quality criteria. Once the system successfully passed all tests, the project entered the actual deployment phase, and the system advanced to the production environment, that hosts the DT-EWS version released to the users.

The final phase, Co-validation, involves the presentation of the completed system to users. This step is crucial. On one hand, to showcase the complete system to the users and give them a tutorial on how to operate with it. On the other hand, to ascertain the users' satisfaction with the delivered functionalities and overall system performance. At this juncture, the creation of user credentials occurred, enabling secure and controlled access for authorized users to interact with the digital twin in the operational environment. If users indicate dissatisfaction or identify issues at this stage, the process loops back to address these concerns before re-presentation. Upon gaining initial user approval, user-specific tests are conducted to evaluate the practical application and usability of the system in realistic scenarios. If the user tests identify problems, the system again revisits the presentation step for further refinement and testing.

Once user testing yields satisfactory results, structured feedback sessions are initiated. These sessions allow for detailed user feedback, ensuring that the system not only meets functional requirements but also effectively supports the specific operational contexts of the coastal cities. Persistent issues or further user suggestions identified during feedback sessions prompt the system to loop back for additional refinement and validation. Ultimately, once all user feedback is positive, confirming full satisfaction with the system's functionality, usability, and robustness, the digital twin system is declared fully delivered and operational.

This rigorous, iterative process ensured that the digital twin system has been thoroughly vetted, meeting user expectations comprehensively, and robustly supporting urban planning strategies to enhance resilience against sea and riverine floods in the CCLLs. Most importantly, there was not the need for major system improvements, since the DT-EWS system met the users' expectations, thanks to the codesign activities that have been carried out at the beginning of the project in Task T8.1.

5.2. System technical deployment

5.2.1. System components and deployment environment

As detailed in Figure 5, the SCORE DT USE-EWS system is a comprehensive solution designed to simulate flood scenarios, thanks to the USE subsystem, and provide early warnings, by means of the EWS subsystem. Its modular architecture ensures robust and scalable operation, with components strategically deployed across collaborating institutions.

Figure 5. Block scheme of the system deployment and connection with internal subsystems and other external infrastructures.

Among the system architecture and components, the SCORE DT USE-EWS system is equipped with the following key modules:

- WEB-GUI: The web-based graphical user interface, serving as the primary interaction point for users to simulate scenarios and consult pre-alarms.
- API: The Application Programming Interface, providing the backend services consumed by the WEB-GUI.
- SIM: The simulator module, responsible for executing user-defined flood scenarios.
- MAP: The mapping service, delivering graphical representations of simulation results.

- EWS: The Early Warning System support module, managing sensor data, meteorological forecasts, and risk assessment.

The deployment environment of the system is also composed of different parts. The WEB-GUI is hosted on a dedicated server at the University College of Dublin, ensuring accessibility and performance for front-end operations. All other modules—API, SIM, MAP, and EWS—are deployed and executed on a server located at M.B.I. srl. This centralized hosting for the core processing modules streamlines data flow and inter-module communication.

5.2.2. Backend Services and Containerization

The API, SIM, MAP, and EWS modules are built upon a suite of interconnected services, all operating within a containerized environment provided by Docker Compose [13]. This containerization approach ensures that applications run in isolated, self-contained, and operating system-independent environments, enhancing portability and simplifying deployment and management.

The services within these modules include:

- API Service: Implemented using a Django application coupled with Gunicorn for efficient request handling.
- Database: PostgreSQL serves as the relational database management system for persistent data storage.
- Scheduler: Celery is utilized as the distributed task queue for managing and executing background tasks.
- Workers: Celery workers are employed to perform computationally intensive tasks such as simulating scenarios, collecting data from sensors and weather services, and selecting potential future scenarios.
- Messaging Broker: RabbitMQ facilitates asynchronous communication between different services.
- Map Server: MapServer is used to render and serve geographical data.

Each module plays a critical role in the overall system's functionality. The SIM module specifically handles the execution of user flood scenario simulations, leveraging the LISFLOOD-FP program for its hydrological modeling capabilities. The MAP module, on the other hand, is integral to the WEB-GUI, providing the necessary services to display geolocated simulation results, including flooded areas and risk maps. The EWS module, instead, is organized into various periodic processes that:

- Read sensor data from the territory using the above-mentioned TERO SensorThings API.
- Acquire meteorological forecasts for areas of interest through APIs provided by local services in the study areas.
- Select the most probable scenario from appropriately simulated and pre-loaded scenarios within the system.
- Communicate whether the selected future scenario poses a risk to the population and/or infrastructure.

6. INTERACTIONS WITH USERS

6.1. Massa

6.1.1. System presentation and tutorial

The very first live system demonstration was held for the users of Massa, which has represented the pilot case for the three WP8 frontrunners. The meeting took place on 23/04/2024 and was divided in three parts:

1. A presentation employing a slide deck to outline the user architecture, reporting the description of the USE and EWS subsystem, the GUI, the used inputs, and examples of simulation outputs
2. The live demo of the system, showing the procedure to create a scenario and launch a simulation form the system's GUI
3. A discussion with the users to collect their first feelings and impressions about the DT-EWS system, to ask them some questions that could lead to a system fine-tuning, and to answer their eventual questions as well.

The attendees of the meeting, beyond SCORE WP8 participants (MBI, CNR-ISAC, UCD) and the CCLL core team members, were the local coordinator of the Civil Protection and members of the Environment Management office of the Municipality. Figure 6 shows a picture taken by a CCLL core team member during the meeting.

Figure 6. A picture from the DT-EWS system presentation meeting in Massa (20/09/2025).

During the meeting, a long time has been dedicated to training participants in using the digital twin system. However, on the user's demand, a second meeting was held on 09/07/2024, to better train interactions with the system. At the end of the first meeting there was a session completely dedicated to a discussion on system design and usability. The system developers asked some questions to the users for system fine tuning and to better meet the users' requirements.

Below, the questions to the users are presented. The answers and their evaluation from WP8' side is a topic related to system validation and are reported in [18].

1. Which figure should receive EWS module alert messages?
2. In what context might EWS module alert messages arrive?
3. Who will be the authorized users to first use and test the system?
4. Every 15', the EWS gives as output the most probable scenario. If there is at least one in the associated maps where a cell exceeds the alert threshold, the alert is triggered.
 - a. Does an output every 15' minutes have a sufficient frequency?
 - b. What time horizon may be sufficient (3h, 6h...)?
 - c. How to establish alarm thresholds? Starting from how many people affected? As of what magnitude of economic damage?
4. If there are areas of the city that require special attention, which areas? As of what level of flooding?
 - d. Do you prefer danger bands (e.g., yellow/orange/red/black alert)?
 - e. Should the system keep in memory some past hazard maps, even if the time to which they refer has already passed?
5. At the end of the simulations, the USE module outputs a PDF report summarizing the main data of the simulation and its results. Based on it, the user can determine whether the results obtained can be further studied or discarded.
6. Do users find the report useful?
7. Can propose system improvements, e.g., further pieces of information that could be added to the report?
8. What is the best time interval between the frames in the report?
9. At the end of the simulations, the USE module gives as output flood and damage maps.
10. Do you think only the final maps are necessary, (i.e., related to the simulation final instant), or also the intermediate ones can be helpful?
11. If yes, with which granularity?
12. To our knowledge, the only sensor related to the water level of the Frigido River is the one at the Canevara station, far upstream from the study area.
13. Do you have runoff scales/correlation models that allow you to map, after a known time interval, the value read by that sensor into a level/flow rate value at the point of entry of the Frigid River into the study area? If so, can you make these available to the system?
14. Will you install additional level sensors on the minor reticle? If so, will it be possible to get that data?

6.1.2. User feedback session

After allowing some weeks for the users to use the system and get acquainted with it, a user feedback session was been planned for 20/09/2024. During this meeting, the users' comments and observations have been collected. Their inputs have been extremely useful for system improvement. Overall, good acceptance of the system has been noticed on the users' side, and feedback has been positive, with some proposals for some system updates.

6.1.3. Other activities

During the "EBA Training School", a three-day event held in Massa in February 2025, a session has been dedicated to the presentation of the DT-EWS system to city stakeholders that can be interested in the system usage. People from the municipality, including the mayor, were present, along with representatives from associations with social and economic interests in the Massa area. A system presentation and live demo took place, which stimulated the interest of the audience of the DT also as a tool that can facilitate the communication between administrators and citizens.

6.2. Vilanova i la Geltrú

6.2.1. System presentation and tutorial

The second deployment of the DT-EWS was in the CCLL of Vilanova i la Geltrú. The approach was the same as for the pilot case of Massa. A first meeting has been organized for the system deployment, i.e. for the presentation of the DT-EWS to the users of the CCLL, on 29/11/2024. The meeting structure was the same, with a system presentation and general overview, followed by a live demo, with a simulation prepared and launched from the GUI. At the end, a Questions & Answers session took place. It was useful to collect first comments and observations from the users participating to the session. As done in Massa, a list of questions was prepared, more focused on Vilanova, as reported in the following.

1. **Who shall receive the alert messages issued by the EWS module?**
 - In the final version of the DT-EWS, alert messages will comply with the Common Alerting Protocol (CAP) and will be directly sent to people in charge of managing the alert
 - Please provide names and contacts (es. Email address, Whatsapp number)
2. **Who are the authorized users that will test the system?**
 - VNG already gave three names of users, if you want to create other users, please provide names and emails to create their credentials

Please note that, for the moment, each CCLL will have the possibility of launching a simulation at a time. In case a user launches a simulation during the pending simulation of another user, the system will not issue an error message, but will create a queue of simulations and the second one starts automatically when the first is finished.

3. **Every 15 minutes, the EWS outputs the most likely scenario. If in the associated maps there is at least one cell of the map exceeding the alert threshold, the alert is launched.**
 - Is an output each 15 minutes frequent enough?
 - Which time horizon can be long enough (3h, 6h, ...)?
 - How to set alert thresholds? Starting from how many affected people? Starting from which amount of economic damage?
 - If there are city zones deserving particular attention, which ones? Starting from which flooding level?
 - Do you prefer ranges of risk (e.g., Yellow/Orange/Red/Black)?
 - Is it useful for you if the system must keep some past risk maps, although the risk they refer to is already over?
4. **At the end of the simulations, the USE module outputs a human readable PDF report summarizing the main features of the simulation and of its results. Based on that, the user can decide whether those results can be further analysed or discarded.**

- Is the report useful?
 - Would you like to suggest improvements, e.g., further information to be reported?
 - Which is the better interval between the frames included in the report (30', 1h...)?
5. **To our knowledge, there is no sensor for the Torrent de la Piera water discharge or level.**
- Will new sensors be installed?
 - Will you also install sensors on minor rivers? If so, which ones?
6. We designed USE to support administrations in co-design (planificació participativa) with a special focus on Ecosystem-based Adaptation (EbA). For some administrations and projects, co-design is mandatory, while in others it is recommended or not considered at all.
- What is the situation for an administration like Vilanova?
 - If your administration has conducted co-design, was it supported by any technologies?
 - In any case, does DT have the potential to support co-design effectively?
7. **We designed the Early Warning (support) System to help administrations manage early warnings and emergencies related to floods.**
- Could you describe the role of your administration in early warning and emergency management?
 - If your administration is involved in early warning, what technologies support these efforts?
 - Could the EWS assist your administration in its early warning or emergency management duties? In other words, do you find it potentially useful?

6.2.2. Users feedback session

Again in Vilanova i la Geltrú, after leaving to the users some time to get familiar with the presented DT-EWS system, a user feedback session took place on 13/02/2025. In this session the users, represented by a technical employee of the municipality, provided their feedback on the system usability and scope. The content of these comments is reported in [18].

6.2.3. Other activities

A one day-long event took place in Vilanova on 22/05/2025, the 8th edition of “*Governança del litoral del Garraf: Adaptació al canvi climàtic en zones costaneres: reptes i solucions*”. During this event, in which many stakeholders of the city of Vilanova and its surroundings were present, a presentation to the SCORE DT-EWS to a larger audience has been carried out, also reporting on some results related to the validation activities.

6.3. Oarsoaldea

6.3.1. System presentation and tutorial

The system presentation to the users, with the tutorial in system usage, was held in 13/02/2025, with some weeks of delay due to some unexpected setbacks with the hydraulic digital model, revealed by finer system tests, that have eventually been solved. During this meeting, as with the other CCLLs, the system has been thoroughly showcased to the users. They were shown the system architecture along with the needed inputs and outputs, and were instructed on how to create scenarios and launch simulations.

Of course, again a part of the meeting has been devoted to discussion with users that have been requested to answer questions. The questions used in meetings with the other CCLLs, were customized to Oarsoaldea. They were the following.

1. **Who shall receive the alert messages issued by the EWS module?**
 - In the final version of the DT-EWS, alert messages will comply with the Common Alerting Protocol (CAP) and will be directly sent to persons in charge of managing the alert
 - Please provide names and contacts (es. Email address, Whatsapp number)
2. **Who are the authorized users that will test the system?**
 - Oarsoaldea already gave two names of users, if you want to create other users, please provide names and emails to create their credentials

It is foreseen that each CCLL will have the possibility of launching one simulation at a time. In case a user launches a simulation during the pending simulation of another user, the system will not issue an error message, but will create a queue of simulations and the second one starts automatically when the first is finished.

3. **Each 15', the EWS outputs the most likely scenario. If in the associated maps there is at least one cell of the map exceeding the alert threshold, the alert is launched.**
 - Is an output each 15 minutes frequent enough?
 - Which time horizon can be long enough (3h, 6h, ...)?
 - How to set alert thresholds? Starting from how many affected people? Starting from which amount of economic damage?
 - If there are city zones deserving particular attention, which ones? Starting from which flooding level?
 - Do you prefer ranges of risk (e.g., Yellow/Orange/Red/Black)?
 - Is it useful for you if the system must keep some past risk maps, although the risk they refer to is already over?
4. **At the end of the simulations, the USE module outputs a human readable PDF report summarizing the main features of the simulation and of its results. Based on that, the user can decide whether those results can be further analysed or discarded.**
 - Is the report useful?
 - Would you like to suggest improvements, e.g., further information to be reported?

- Which is the better interval between the frames included in the report (30', 1h...)?
5. To our knowledge, there is a sensor for the Oiartzun water discharge and level. The data for the discharge (in m³/s) are not available since March 2023.
- Can these data be made available again?
 - Will you also install sensors on minor rivers? If so, which ones?
6. We designed USE to support administrations in co-design (*planificación participativa*) with a special focus on Ecosystem-based Adaptation (EbA). For some administrations and projects, co-design is mandatory, while in others it is recommended or not considered at all.
- What is the situation for an administration like Oarsoaldea?
 - If your administration has conducted co-design, was it supported by any technologies?
 - In any case, does DT have the potential to support co-design effectively?
7. We designed the Early Warning (support) System (EWS) to help administrations manage early warnings and emergencies related to floods.
- Could you describe the role of your administration in early warning and emergency management?
 - If your administration is involved in early warning, what technologies support these efforts?
 - Could the EWS assist your administration in its early warning or emergency management duties? In other words, do you find it potentially useful?

6.3.2. User feedback session

Also in Oarsoaldea, after allowing users some weeks to familiarize themselves with the system, a feedback session was scheduled for March 24, 2025. During this meeting, users' comments and observations were gathered. Their input proved highly valuable for enhancing the system. Overall, the system was well received by the users, with positive feedback and some suggestions for future updates, like some more pieces of information to be displayed by the GUI regarding the EBAs.

Figure 7. A picture from the stakeholders session held in Oarsoaldea, taken during the DT-EWS live demo (30/05/2025)

6.3.3. Other activities

Finally, a meeting for presenting the system also to the Oarsoaldea CCLL core team and stakeholders took place in May 30th 2025 (see image in Figure 7). The system was explained and showcased to a larger audience, highlighting its potential advantages for decision-making activities. The content of this comments are reported in [18].

7. CONCLUSIONS

The activities related to the deployment and subsequent usage of the SCORE DT-EWS demonstrate that developing coastal resilience in the face of accelerating climate-change impacts demands a twin strategy that marries EBAs with sophisticated digital decision support. Rapid sea-level rise, intensifying storms and shifting rainfall patterns are already outpacing the design limits of traditional grey infrastructure, exposing assets, populations and ecosystems to mounting hydraulic risk.

By restoring or emulating natural buffers such as wetlands, dunes, mangroves and permeable urban surfaces, cities can dissipate wave energy, absorb stormwater and reduce flood extents while simultaneously enhancing biodiversity, improving water quality and delivering recreational and aesthetic benefits; these EBAs also entail lower life-cycle costs than many engineered defences. Yet, unlocking their full value depends on timely information and clear foresight. The SCORE project's DT-EWS platform addresses this need by fusing high-resolution topographic, land-cover and vulnerability maps with real-time sensor feeds, local weather forecasts and short- and medium-range climate projections inside a modular architecture that supports both continuous early warning and interactive "what-if" scenario analysis. Tested through an iterative co-design, co-creation and co-validation process with municipal experts in Massa, Vilanova i la Geltrú and Oarsoaldea, the system proved capable of delivering 15-minute flood-risk updates, customised alert thresholds, dynamic damage maps and autogenerated simulation reports that inform both emergency response and long-term planning.

User engagement was critical: workshops, tutorials, and feedback loops ensured that interface layouts, alert channels, report content, and data priorities aligned with local workflows, regulatory frameworks, and resource constraints, while also revealing gaps—such as insufficient river-level sensors—that need to be addressed to improve model accuracy. The pilot implementations demonstrate that the DT-EWS can adapt to contrasting coastal morphologies and governance contexts, suggesting strong scalability to other cities, provided that baseline geodata, sensor networks, and stakeholder commitment are in place.

Looking forward, the SCORE projects aimed at showing the positive impact of synergies between EBAs application and smart technologies, orchestrated through data-driven tools that translate complex environmental signals into actionable knowledge for planners, civil-protection officers and the wider community. The level of satisfaction of the DT-EWS users is a promising beginning in the way of developing a system with higher technological readiness level, that can guide and support decision-makers in urban environment management and disaster prevention.

The WP8 leader, MBI srl, is willing keep the system running for one year more after the project completion, to let users continue operating with it and to maximise its impact. However, since the DT-EWS system relies on the structures and contributions of three project partners, discussions are ongoing to coordinate their efforts to this aim.

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